

A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF TEAM CHANGE ON EMPLOYEES' EFFICIENCY

Dr. WALEED ELTAYEB OMER KHALID

Assistant Professor, Department of Management, Jazan University, KSA

Dr. SYED MOHAMMAD FAISAL

Assistant Professor, Department of Management, Jazan University, KSA

Dr. AHMAD KHALID KHAN

Assistant Professor, Department of Management, Jazan University, KSA

Dr. ASMA HASHIM

Ex-Researcher, Department of Management, Kalinga University, India

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to determine the effect that team change has on employee efficiency and the actions that the organization can take to increase employee efficiency in the event of team change. The study was conducted utilizing a descriptive technique, which enables the collection of in-depth data on certain themes via the use of several perspectives. The research surveyed 60 respondents from the hotel business, 40 of whom were workers and 20 of whom were managers. The methods of convenient and purposive sampling were employed to pick respondents based on their willingness and capacity to answer to the questionnaire. 15% of respondents strongly agreed that collaborating with a new team boosted an employee's efficiency, 18.3% agreed, 26.7 percent were unsure (neutral), and 56.7 percent disapproved. Thus, it can be argued that a change in team composition might have a detrimental effect on the employee's efficiency and performance, since the employee is used to the team members with whom they operate, and a change in team composition may disrupt their usual operations. As a result of the shift in team, the employee's stress levels may rise, creating an atmosphere of pessimism and cynicism that distracts them from their task. Thus, in the event of a team turnover, the leader must be very supportive in order for the employee to perform effectively and fearlessly.

Keywords: Team change, Employee, Efficiency, Change Management, Organization

Introduction

In this pandemic scenario, when the working has been disturbed, everything changes very rapidly. The business firms are making one and other changes simultaneously for the smooth working of the organization. During the epidemic, workers were fired owing to global lockdown and company limitations, causing team member changes. There were various reasons behind the team change, and this change in the team has affected the team members in one way. There were many issues faced by the new team members, such as coping with new employers and coordinating with new team members. They had faced difficulty in adopting the culture of new team members, which was a challenging situation for them.

Literature review

Change in an organization

Change in an organization is the transition from one state of affairs to another. There are many ways in which organizations can change (Weiner, B. J. (2009). There may be significant changes in a company's structure, strategy, policies, procedures, technologies, or culture. There are many ways that an organization may change. "It may be planned, or it may be forced upon them." An organization may undergo radical change affecting the way it functions, or it may undergo incremental change (R. T. (2005). Regardless of how the change is enacted, it involves letting go of the old ways in which work was done and adapting to the new ways. It is, therefore, fundamentally a people-management process.

Organizations often form change teams to deal with significant planned or unplanned changes (Burke, W. W. (2017). This kind of team has been separated because of its importance. Often, the senior management team oversees and sponsors changes, which might be referred to as a change team. Change teams are sometimes created as special project teams for implementing improvements. Sometimes, the change team is a parallel team whose function is to provide feedback on the impact of the changes on the organization (Sun, M. et al. (2006). The terminology used by different organizations differs, so a project team has achieved a change within one organization, but within another organization, a change team has achieved a project.

People-oriented change management is also becoming increasingly important to organizations, as it is more probable to succeed. It can be helpful to create a parallel team composed of representatives from the whole workforce to assess and respond to the effects of the changes on people (Cameron et al. (2019).

Factors which influence change

What is the cause of this change? Organizational change: What is the cause? Changes in an organization may result from a single factor, or they may be caused by several factors (Van Oosterhout et al. (2006). A leader can have a vision of the future in financial terms or economically, politically, socially, or legally. In addition to these, and many others, there are two groups of factors that influence change: internal and external (Fowler (2013).

Internal Factors affecting change

Factors internal to an organization are those which come from within it. Because these factors fall within the organization's scope, they are predictable (Koberg, C. S. et al. (2003).

Management and leadership are aware and understand the internal factors that influence change and have a strategy to deal with these.

A few key factors impacting organizational change are as follows.

- **Vision:** An organization may have a vision. To achieve its vision, such organizations constantly make changes. The vision of these organizations is also often revised and

redefined. This force makes it possible for us to accept and implement changes (Cabrera et al. (2001).

- **Values:** Change is also driven by an organization's core values. Changing organizational strategies and processes can often be influenced by values such as gender balance, cultural diversity, and ethnic diversity.
- **Managerial changes:** Changes in environmental conditions are accompanied by changes in management personnel. It is necessary to replace old managers due to retirements, promotions, transfers, and dismissals (Denis et al. (1995). An integral part of every manager's job description is to bring new ideas to the organization and new ways of working. Within the organization, relationships are more important. In particular, informal relationships change due to changes in management personnel. However, attitudes change despite no changes in personnel. Consequently, an organization must adapt to change accordingly (Meyer et al. (2007).
- **Inadequacy of Existing Organization:** Change may sometimes be needed due to inadequacies in the current organizational and operational structure. Deficits may manifest themselves in an unmanageable managerial span, an enormous number of managerial levels, a lack of coordination between departments, delays in communication, the proliferation of committees, an inability to uniformly implement policies, and so on (Berman, L. (2015).
- **Workforce nature:** Workforce nature has changed over time. Various generations have emphasized different values in the workplace (Chen et al. (2008). Over fifty-five-year-old employees value their relationships with their employers. The actions of women in their late thirties and early forties are characterized by their self-centeredness. Younger generations of workers are dedicated to their careers. Fast-changing demographics also affect the workforce (Hajkowicz et al. (2016). Today, new worker generations have better education, place a greater focus on human values, and are more critical of management authority. It is a challenge for managers to direct their behavior towards organizational goals since their behavior has become more complex. Also, high employee turnover puts pressure on management (Carmeli, A. (2003).
- **As a preventative measure:** Organizations often change to avoid the development of inertia or rigidity (Yi et al. (2016). Every conscious manager recognizes that every organization should be dynamic because the best management cannot be found in a single tool. As a result, the staff becomes accustomed to change, and there is less resistance to change when significant changes occur within the organization.
- **Organizational culture:** Organizations' cultures have a significant impact on their future. A dynamic workplace culture in which leaders encourage creativity increases the likelihood of an organization accepting and implementing change (Lowell, K. R. (2016).

- **Core expertise:** A company's core competence dictates change as well. It is implausible that the organization will disrupt itself if it is vital in one technical area.
- **Leadership:** Leadership changes are sometimes the cause of organizational change. Whenever a new leader takes over, the organization's vision, strategies, and working culture change (Kanter, R. M. (2003). New leadership largely influences change because it is an influential internal factor.
- **Performance:** Change is most likely driven by this factor. When a business is not performing well, good leaders change their approach. There follows a dramatic change in the role and responsibilities of various players within the organization to perform better in the industry.
- **Employees:** Employee skills and attitude are important factors determining a company's ability to make changes. It is more likely that an organization will successfully manage change if employees accept change and have the appropriate skills.

External factors affecting change

The environment in which organizations operate is vast. These are external to organizations, so they are mainly out of control (Chubb et al. (1988). These include customers, government, policy, laws, social norms, technology, competition, economy, etc. The lack of knowledge and understanding of external change is something different from control. This also drives organizational change due to external factors. Change management is challenging for external factors because they are unpredictable compared to internal factors (Koberg et al. (2003). The following factors impact organizational change in critical ways.

- **New opportunities:** Business opportunities arise from economic growth. Market opportunities allow organizations to expand. This can only be achieved by changing strategies, acquiring new expertise, and hiring new staff members.
- **Fashion:** Changes are dictated by current trends. People are increasingly aware of the importance of health and hygiene. As a result, organizations offer healthier products to their clients and demonstrate that they care about their health.
- **Competition:** Every day, competition is becoming more intense. Innovative marketing strategies and new marketing tools allow companies to disrupt market trends. To survive and thrive in the market, every actor in the industry must respond to and develop their strategy.
- **New Technology:** In addition to technology, other factors shape changes. Technology upgrades are essential for organizations to stay competitive in the digital world. A ten-year-old organization does not have to be active on online marketing platforms today; this is necessary nowadays.

- **Government regulation:** Various laws and regulations, such as a government's trade policy, taxation, and industry-specific regulations, affect how businesses operate. To stay on top of government policies, organizations should stay adaptable.
- **Politics and economy:** Political and economic factors affect business internally and externally. It only takes one incident to damage an entire country's economy. Politics and the economy must be closely followed and analyzed by organizations to respond to changing conditions.
- **Social change:** Social change includes norms, education, urbanization, and migration. Furthermore, social change is another decisive external factor that impacts the environment, pushing organizations to make changes.

Impact of change on employees

Financial concerns, mergers or acquisitions, expanding markets, creating room for growth, or simply shifting business models are reasons for changing teams (Johnson et al. (2010)). It is common for employees to struggle with change, harming business. To understand their reactions to your company's changes, put yourself in their shoes. That way, "firms will be able to minimize risks to your company and unnecessary stress on your employees."

"A 2017 study by the American Psychological Association found that 55 % of people who reported experiencing organizational upheaval at work reported feeling chronic stress, compared with 22 % of those who said they did not experience organizational turmoil" (Wynen et al. (2017)). In a study of employees who experienced organizational changes at work, 35 % were experiencing physical symptoms caused by stress at work. The study found that only 8 % experienced the same symptoms when there was no organizational change. Several factors can increase stress levels, including perceptions of injustice, "a lack of timely communication by management, and fear of future changes."

Payroll and benefits are often the first places to cut back when companies look for ways to save money. Some employees are compelled to leave the company for another job (Miceli et al. (1992)).

Often, the employees remain resentful, whether they remain out of their own volition or cannot find work elsewhere. Performance decreases as motivation decreases. It may even cause employees to become enraged that they deliberately sabotage the company (Groth et al. (2012)).

Our experience has been that employees generally fall into two groups when organizational changes are announced, mainly when downsizing will occur: those trying to control their fate and those starting the process of leaving before the changes are implemented. Usually, people in charge will dig in, increase productivity, meet deadlines, and do everything to avoid losing their jobs in the face of change (Salerno et al. (2008)).

While the rest of the staff avoids the changes, they cope with it. Some employees may take long lunch breaks, come late and leave early, or not come into the office (Perlow et al.

(2001). "The organization can expect employees to take more sick days while carrying out the organizational changes, whether they are looking for a new job or avoiding the office."

Many employees' lives may be radically altered due to organizational changes (Howe et al. (2020). Salary cuts may negatively impact some employees, loss of benefits, downgrades in their job status, job loss, or relocation to another city, state, or country. These changes can impact employees who are raising families (Abdurakhmanova et al. (2019).

Communication and compassionate treatment of the affected employees should be the leading way to handle these changes and keep the morale of the rest of the employees high.

According to a survey released by the American Psychological Association, "Americans who have been affected by the organizational change are more likely to report chronic work stress, are less likely to trust their employer, and are more likely to say they plan to leave the organization within the next year" (Meyer, I. H. (2003).

A recent survey conducted by APA of workers' well-being and work experiences shows that half (50%) have already experienced organizational changes in the past year, are experiencing organizational changes now, or anticipate organizational changes shortly. In March, an online survey conducted by Harris Poll featured 1,500 full- and part-time employed U.S. adults.

The likelihood of chronic work stress was more than twice as high for workers who had experienced recent, current, or anticipated change than those who did not (55% versus 22%). Physical health symptoms were also four times as common among workers experiencing recent or current changes (34% versus 8%).

When asked about work-life conflicts, "those who reported recent or current changes were more likely to say they experienced work-life conflict (39 vs. 12 % for work interfering with non-work obligations and 32 vs. 7 % for home and family responsibilities interfering with work), felt cynical and negative toward others during the workday (35 vs. 11 %) and ate or smoked more than those who did not (29 % vs. 8 %)" (Buddhapriya, S. (2009).

As a result of the poll, employees' views and experiences at work may be affected by workplace reforms. Comparatively, workers who reported being influenced by recent, present, "or prospective organizational changes reported lower levels of job satisfaction than employees who did not report any recent, current, or future organizational changes (71 % vs. 81 %)" (Burke, R. J. (2006).

More than three times as many working "Americans who reported a recent or current change did not trust their employer (34% vs.12%) and more than three times as many said they planned on seeking employment outside the organization within the next year (46% vs.15%) than those who did not report any recent", current, or anticipated change (Castro et al. (2017).

The research found that workers' feelings are influenced by their perceptions of the changes' reasons and the likelihood of success. Most U.S. workers are skeptical of changes, believing that management has a hidden purpose (29%), that their goals and motives are not what they claim (31%), and they try to hide the genuine reasons for the changes (29%).

Often, leaders misjudge the impact that changes have on their workers. When it comes to the results of organizational reforms, working Americans are likewise skeptical. Fewer than half (43%) of employees believed that improvements would have the desired impact, and over three-quarters (76%) were skeptical that changes would be successful (28 % each) (Betts, R. K. (2009).

APA's Center for Organizational Excellence director David W. Ballard, PsyD, MBA, believes that change is inevitable in companies and that leaders typically underestimate the impact of such changes on employees. In the process, "managers may undermine the very change initiatives they are attempting to promote if they destroy their connection with employees, ratchet up stress levels, and create an environment of pessimism and cynicism."

Impact on the efficiency and productivity of employees

Researchers have conducted several studies that examined the impact of organizational change on employee performance. "The research on the impacts of organizational change on the employee performance of the postal service in Kenya. "He found that organizational change negatively influenced employee performance. Tech has affected employee performance the most and positively (Wanza et al. (2016). As a result of the internship program provided by the organization (Postal Corporation), more employment opportunities have been gained. The motivated staff has been able to perform better due to this. It is recommended that public organizations seeking change emphasize the urgency and necessity of those changes in simple, understandable terms. The authors applied a descriptive statistics and correlation analysis method to the research on organizational change and employee performance in the banking sector in Pakistan by Ahmed, Rehman, Asad, Hussain, and Bilal (Ahmed et al. (2013). The study found that organizational change positively affects the performance of employees in Pakistani banks. In order to know how organizational change affects employee performance on a large scale, further research needs to be conducted in various sectors. A study conducted by Khan and Jabbar examined the factors affecting an employee's performance in the Pakistani corporate sector (Farooqi et al. (2013). The study found that work-life conflict negatively affected employee performance while working conditions showed a weak correlation.

Employee performance was strongly influenced by leadership and compensation.

Kansal and Singh examined Maruti Suzuki employees' performance (Singh et al. (2016). Among gender, departments, and designations, the organizational change affected employee performance significantly. According to the study, positive attitudes and practices in the workplace result in improved performance. Changing the environment affects employees' attitudes, as shown by their performance. An employee motivation study by Tefera and Mutambara was conducted at a country club in Kwazulu Natal to determine the effects of organizational changes on employee motivation (Tefera et al. (2016). The study's key finding was that the management did not create opportunities for employees to participate.

Demotivation may have resulted from employees feeling excluded from the decision-making process. A lack of communication in the organization exacerbates this problem.

Organizational change was perceived as a means to attaining the club's goals, but financial targets were not met. Although this change in organizational culture had a positive impact on employee motivation, the challenge for managers was to retain that motivation.

Using technology changes, organizational leadership, structure, and culture, "Wanza and Nkuraru looked at the impact of change management on employee performance" (Wanza et al. (2016). According to the study, structures and leadership also had a positive impact on employees' performance. Moreover, the study found that technological changes are a significant contributor to employees' performance owing to the rapid development of technology around the globe which eases work and enhances efficiency. A solid organizational culture fosters synergy and drive, enhancing employee performance and promoting teamwork, as Wanza and Nkuraru argue.

Several aspects of the organizational culture, including structure, leadership, technology, and technology utilization, positively affect employee performance. Khan & Jabbar found that employee growth improved employee productivity and efficiency (Khan et al. (2013). How the employee performs is determined by his or her willingness and openness to do the job.

For a company to be successful and profitable, employee performance is crucial. In Chien's opinion, "a successful organization requires employees who are willing to do more than their usual responsibilities and achieve results that are above and beyond their goals. "An increasingly competitive environment requires employees to perform at their highest levels in order for the organization to be effective.

As more companies face challenges in the modern business world, they must focus more on enhancing employee performance (Gruman et al. (2011). Employees must have the freedom to design their jobs and roles to perform at their best. The employee will find job opportunities that suit their skills, values, and needs in this way. A downsizing innovation will drop employees' performance.

Objectives

- To study the importance of teamwork in an organization.
- To know the impact of team, change on employee efficiency.
- To find out the measures for increasing employee efficiency during the change in the team.

Methodology

The research has been carried out using the descriptive approach as it assists in gathering in-depth data on particular subjects by making descriptions of various angles. The research included 60 respondents from the hotel business, 40 of whom were workers and 20 were managers. "The convenient and purposive sampling was the techniques which were used to select respondents based on the fact and their willingness and ability to respond to the questionnaire."

Data Collection

The primary data has been used for the study, which was gathered using the questionnaires based upon the rating scale. In the study, data were collected primarily through questionnaires. In order to enhance the validity of the data, this is necessary.

Data Analysis

The research was carried out with the use of qualitative data analysis. These percentages and frequencies in ages are used in data analysis.

- To identify the importance of teamwork in increasing employees' efficiency.

Table 1. Importance of teamwork on employee's efficiency

(Responses)	% o f respondents and number of respondents									
	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
Variables	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Employees gain knowledge and skills when they work as a team.	38	63	18	30	-	-	4	6.7	-	-
Teams are motivated by managers.	22	37	26	43	10	17	2	3.4	-	-
Employees who work in teams are more efficient.	12	20	38	63	8	13	-	-	2	3.3
Members of the team are equally stressed out by work.	20	33	12	20	14	23	12	20	2	3.3
Team members have equal opportunities to develop their skills and confidence.	16	27	26	43	14	23	2	3.2	2	3.1
Individuals are intimidated by team members in order to limit their participation and Reduces team motivation and involvement.	4	6.6	10	17	22	37	16	27	8	13.3

- To identify the effects of team, change on employees.

Table 2. Effects of team change on employee's efficiency

(Responses)	% of respondents and number of respondents									
Variables	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Employees gain knowledge and skills through team changing.	5	8.30	10	16.70	20	33.30	15	25.00	10	16.70
Managers motivate employees who are new in teams.	8	13.30	12	20.00	15	25.00	14	23.30	11	18.30
An employee's efficiency increases when they work with a new team.	9	15.00	11	18.30	16	26.70	24	40.00	10	16.70
New team members are equally under pressure.	7	11.70	9	15.00	34	56.70	7	11.70	3	5.00
Team members are all given equal opportunities to participate in the development process confidence and skills.	8	13.30	7	11.70	20	33.30	22	36.70	3	5.00
The team intimidates new members, limiting their participation and this decreases team participation and motivation.	17	28.30	13	21.70	15	25.00	9	15.00	6	10.00

Results

The results of Table 1 reflect 63.2% of respondents strongly agreeing that Employees gain knowledge and skills when they work together, followed by 30.1% of respondents agreeing, 6.7% disagreeing, none were sure or strongly disagreeing, 36.6% strongly agreeing that managers motivate teams, 16.6% did not know (neutral), and 43.4% disagreed, while none were strongly disagreeing.

In addition, 20% of the respondents strongly agreed that working in teams makes employees more efficient, 63.4% strongly agreed, 13.2% neutral (neutral), 3.3% strongly disagreed. In

contrast, nobody disagreed; furthermore, 26.8% of respondents strongly agree that team members have equal opportunities to develop their skills and confidence, followed by 43.2%, 23.4% unsure (neutral), 3.1% strongly disagree, and 3.2% disagree.

Also, 6.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that team members intimidate individuals in order to limit their participation and reduce motivation and engagement among the team members, compared to 16.8% disagreeing, 36.6% not sure (neutral), 27% disagreeing, and 13.3% strongly disagreeing, and

30% strongly agreed that team members were equally stressed by work, 23.3% were unsure if they were stressed (neutral), 20% disagreed, and 3.3% strongly disagreed.

Table 2. Results indicate that 8.3% of respondents strongly agreed that employees gain skills and knowledge through team changes, while 16.7% agreed and 25% disagreed, while 16.7% disagreed strongly and 33.3% remained neutral, while 13.3% of respondents strongly concurred. Twenty percent agreed, 25 percent were not sure (neutral), and 41.6% disagreed that managers motivate new team members.

One-fifth of the respondents strongly agreed that employees become more efficient when they work in a new team, 18.3% of the respondents agreed, 26.7% were unsure (neutral), and 56.7% disagreed, and 13.3% strongly agreed that team members are given equal opportunities to participate in the development process, while 11.7% agreed, 33.3% were not sure (neutral), 5% strongly disagreed, and 36.7% disagree.

A further 28.3% of respondents strongly agreed that the team intimidates new members, which limits their involvement and decreases team participation and motivation, with 21.7% stating that this is true, 25% saying they are not sure (neutral), 15% disagreeing, and 10% strongly disagree, as well as 11.7% strongly agreeing that new team members are also under pressure. In comparison, 15% agree, 56.7% were not sure (neutral), 11.7% disagree and 5% strongly disagree.

The study's breadth is constrained by a lack of funding and an oath signed by respondents to protect the confidentiality of the organization in which they work. The targeted groups were least interested in sharing the data. There were times when they resisted providing the requested information. Although there were limitations to the study, detailed observations were made to reduce these limitations and make acceptable conclusions.

Discussion

Implementing the transformation process successfully within an organization can be one of the biggest challenges of all. Historically, team change projects have been characterized by a 60 to 70 per cent failure rate since the 1970s. Leadership skills, however, can greatly increase the chance of success.

It is natural for employees to resist change because they are only human. The wrong way to handle a team change can cause more than just annoyance and make them uncomfortable. The impact of stress is not limited to the workplace; it also affects health, productivity, and quality of work life. There's a risk of losing the organization's best employees.

In order to succeed with any change management process, you need to keep employees at the forefront. In order to provide a positive change management process, here are some ideas for minimizing negative effects of change on employees: Change management is never easy, and is just messy, chaotic, and unpredictable, so many organizations hire human resource consultants and specialists to help with the process. There is a high probability of failure with this approach. It is perceived by employees as someone who is outside the company and doesn't quite understand it.

Immediately, negativity is created. In order for managers to take responsibility within the process, it's better to strengthen their leadership skills and enable them to manage change.

Changes might be desired by an employee, but that doesn't mean that they will happen in reality once the organization unravels processes and systems, and possibly redeploys staff.

Taking the current workload and resources into account, chart a roadmap for change that reflects them. In addition to their current workload, employees may feel drowning in work as a result of implementing large-scale changes. Misinformation and gossip spreading among employees in absence of regular and clear communication from management is one of the worst things that can happen during a change management process. In order to avoid this the leader must ensure that the entire workforce is informed by implementing a communications strategy and using a variety of communication tools. Keeping employees up to date is essential, even if there is nothing new to report, so they are aware of the progress.

Conclusion

Thus, it can be concluded that change in the team can affect the efficiency and performance of the employee badly as the employee is habitual of the teammates with whom they are working, and a change in the team may affect their routine activities. Hence, they encounter many things while working with the new changes. Maybe the new team member with whom the employee has to work is not comfortable, the new leader is not supportive, or maybe they are rude. Therefore, due to change in the team, the employee may ratchet up stress levels and create a climate of negativity and cynicism in the process, which would distract them from their work. So in case of a team change, the leader needs to be very supportive so that the employee can work efficiently without any fear.

References

1. Abdurakhmanova, G., & Abdurakhmanov, K. (2019). Labor Migration of the Population and Evaluation of Supply Chain on the Labor Market. Архив научных исследований.
2. Ahmed, Z., Rehman, Z. U., Asad, A., Hussain, N., & Bilal, A. (2013). The impact of organizational change on the employee's performance in banking sector of Pakistan. Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, 1(1), 1-12.
3. Berman, L. (2015). The Office of Management and Budget and the presidency, 1921-1979. Princeton University Press.
4. Betts, R. K. (2009). Enemies of intelligence: Knowledge and power in American national security. Columbia University Press.
5. Buddhapriya, S. (2009). Work-family challenges and their impact on career decisions: A study of Indian women professionals. Vikalpa, 34(1), 31-46.

6. Burke, R. J. (Ed.). (2006). *Research companion to working time and work addiction*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
7. Burke, W. W. (2017). *Organization change: Theory and practice*. Sage publications.
8. Cabrera, Á., Cabrera, E. F., & Barajas, S. (2001). The key role of organizational culture in a multi-system view of technology-driven change. *International Journal of Information Management*, 21(3), 245-261.
9. Cameron, E., & Green, M. (2019). *Making sense of change management: A complete guide to the models, tools and techniques of organizational change*. Kogan Page Publishers.
10. Carmeli, A. (2003). The relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitudes, behavior and outcomes: An examination among senior managers. *Journal of managerial Psychology*.
11. Castro, C. A., Kintzle, S., & Hassan, A. (2017). *The state of the American veteran*. Los Angeles, CA: Center for Innovation and Research on Veterans and Military Families, School of Social Work, University of California.
12. Chen, P. J., & Choi, Y. (2008). Generational differences in work values: a study of hospitality management. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*.
13. Chubb, J. E., & Moe, T. M. (1988). Politics, markets, and the organization of schools. *American political science review*, 82(4), 1065-1087.
14. Denis, D. J., & Denis, D. K. (1995). Performance changes following top management dismissals. *The Journal of finance*, 50(4), 1029-1057.
15. Farooqi, H., Patel, H., Aslam, H. M., Ansari, I. Q., Khan, M., Iqbal, N., & Asad, N. (2013). Effect of Facebook on the life of Medical University students. *International archives of medicine*, 6(1), 1-8.
16. Fowler, A. (Ed.). (2013). *Striking a balance: A guide to enhancing the effectiveness of non-governmental organisations in international development*. Routledge.
17. Groth, M., & Grandey, A. (2012). From bad to worse: Negative exchange spirals in employee–customer service interactions. *Organizational Psychology Review*, 2(3), 208-233.
18. Gruman, J. A., & Saks, A. M. (2011). Performance management and employee engagement. *Human resource management review*, 21(2), 123-136.
19. Hajkowicz, S. A., Reeson, A., Rudd, L., Bratanova, A., Hodgers, L., Mason, C., & Boughen, N. (2016). *Tomorrow's digitally enabled workforce: Megatrends and scenarios for jobs and employment in Australia over the coming twenty years*. Australian Policy Online.
20. Howe, D. C., Chauhan, R. S., Soderberg, A. T., & Buckley, M. R. (2020). Paradigm shifts caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. *Organizational dynamics*, 100804.
21. Johnson, M. W., & Lafley, A. G. (2010). *Seizing the white space: Business model innovation for growth and renewal*. Harvard Business Press.
22. Kanter, R. M. (2003). *Challenge of organizational change: How companies experience it and leaders guide it*. Simon and Schuster.
23. Khan, M. M., & Jabbar, M. (2013). Determinants of employee's performance in the corporate sector: Case of an emerging market. *Business and Management Research*, 2(3), 25-32.
24. Koberg, C. S., Detienne, D. R., & Heppard, K. A. (2003). An empirical test of environmental, organizational, and process factors affecting incremental and radical innovation. *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 14(1), 21-45.
25. Koberg, C. S., Detienne, D. R., & Heppard, K. A. (2003). An empirical test of environmental, organizational, and process factors affecting incremental and radical innovation. *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 14(1), 21-45.
26. Lowell, K. R. (2016). An application of complexity theory for guiding organizational change. *The Psychologist-Manager Journal*, 19(3-4), 148.
27. Meyer, I. H. (2003). Prejudice, social stress, and mental health in lesbian, gay, and bisexual populations: conceptual issues and research evidence. *Psychological bulletin*, 129(5), 674.
28. Meyer, J. P., Srinivas, E. S., Lal, J. B., & Topolnytsky, L. (2007). Employee commitment and support for an organizational change: Test of the three-component model in two cultures. *Journal of occupational and organizational psychology*, 80(2), 185-211.

29. Miceli, M. P., & Near, J. P. (1992). *Blowing the whistle: The organizational and legal implications for companies and employees*. Lexington Books.
30. Perlow, L. A. (2001). Time to coordinate: Toward an understanding of work-time standards and norms in a multicountry study of software engineers. *Work and Occupations*, 28(1), 91-111.
31. R. T. (2005). Organizational change management: A critical review. *Journal of change management*, 5(4), 369-380.
32. Salerno, A., & Brock, L. (2008). *The change cycle: How people can survive and thrive in organizational change*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
33. Singh, P., Kansal, A., & Carliell-Marquet, C. (2016). Energy and carbon footprints of sewage treatment methods. *Journal of environmental management*, 165, 22-30.
34. Sun, M., Fleming, A., Senaratne, S., Motawa, I., & Yeoh, M. L. (2006). A change management toolkit for construction projects. *Architectural Engineering and Design Management*, 2(4), 261-271.
35. Tefera, O., & Mutambara, E. (2016). Effect of organizational changes on employees' motivation at a Country Club in Kwazulu Natal: from the employees' participation perspectives. *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*, 5(1), 1-14.
36. Van Oosterhout, M., Waarts, E., & van Hillegersberg, J. (2006). Change factors requiring agility and implications for IT. *European journal of information systems*, 15(2), 132-145.
37. Wanza, S. L., & Nkuraru, J. K. (2016). Influence of change management on employee performance: A case of university of Eldoret, Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 7(4), 190-199.
38. Wanza, S. L., & Nkuraru, J. K. (2016). Influence of change management on employee performance: A case of university of Eldoret, Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 7(4), 190-199.
39. Weiner, B. J. (2009). A theory of organizational readiness for change. *Implementation science*, 4(1), 1-9.
40. Wynen, J., Verhoest, K., & Kleizen, B. (2017). More reforms, less innovation? The impact of structural reform histories on innovation-oriented cultures in public organizations. *Public Management Review*, 19(8), 1142-1164.
41. Yi, S., Knudsen, T., & Becker, M. C. (2016). Inertia in routines: A hidden source of organizational variation. *Organization Science*, 27(3), 782-800.